

Spectrophotometric Studies of Fe(III) Complexes with N-Benzoyl N-metasulphonatophenyl Hydroxylamine

A K MAJUMDAR, A K CHAKRABURTTY and S K PANIGRAHI

Department of Chemistry, Jadavpur University, Calcutta-32

Manuscript received 8 October 1975; accepted 30 March 1976

In course of study of the effects of substitution of $-SO_3H$ group in different positions of N-Benzoyl N-phenyl hydroxylamine and its analogues the complexes formed by Fe(III) ion with N-Benzoyl N-meta sulphonato phenyl hydroxylamine have been studied spectrophotometrically. The complexes viz, 1:1 (violet), 1:2 (wine-red) and 1:3 (orange) are formed in the pH ranges 0.7 to 2.5, 2.7 to 4.1 and 4.2 to 6.8 respectively having respective absorption maxima at 500, 480 and 450 nm. The wine-red complex obeys Beer's law; the optimum range, evaluated from the standard curve, is 4.0 to 13.0 ppm of Fe. The compositions of the complexes have been determined by Job's method and interferences due to diverse ions have been studied.

BPHA and its analogues react with many metal ions and their extensive and manifold analytical applications have been described in details in a recent monograph by Majumdar¹. All these reagents are generally sparingly soluble in water but soluble in organic solvents.

The introduction of a sulphonic acid group is likely to enhance the aqueous solubility of such reagents. Attempts are, therefore, being made to prepare and use various sulphonated BPHA derivatives so that spectrophotometric studies can be done with water as the solvent. So far two such compounds have been prepared and used

- (1) Sodium N-benzoyl N-phenyl hydroxylamino benzene (para) sulphonate (BPAHS)² has been used for the study of Fe(III) and U(VI) complexes.
- (2) N(Benzoyl-2 sodium sulphonate) N-phenylhydroxylamine³ has been utilized for the spectrophotometric estimation of Ti(IV).

It has been our endeavour to prepare the sodium salt of N-benzoyl N-phenylhydroxylamino benzene (meta) sulphonic acid and study spectrophotometrically its reaction with various metal ions.

Preparation of the reagent

Nitrobenzene was sulphonated by oleum (20%) at a temperature of 70°-100° to prepare the meta nitrobenzene sulphonic acid which on treatment with NaCl produced its Na salt. The product on filtration gave sodium salt of meta nitrobenzene sulphonic acid in the form of cake which retains sufficient sulphuric acid⁴.

The acidic cake was dissolved in a little water to obtain a saturated solution and solid NaHCO₃ was added pinch by pinch until the solution became

slightly alkaline. The solution was then treated with Zn dust and NH₄Cl to prepare the hydroxylamine derivative, which was then filtered to remove the precipitated zinc oxide.

The filtrate was taken in a beaker, cooled by ice, and treated with solid NaHCO₃ and benzoyl chloride. The product contained yellowish solution and white ppt, stirred for 30 min, allowed to settle and filtered. The residue was washed with little rectified spirit and again recrystallised from rectified spirit. The white product was dried in a desiccator and analysed.

Analysis

Percentage of	Calculated for mono sodium-derivative	Calculated for disodium-derivative	Experimental results
	(1 : 3) $NaO_3S.C_6H_4.$ NOH $C_6H_5.CO$	(1 : 3) $NaO_3S.C_6H_4.$ NONa $C_6H_5.CO$	
Nitrogen	4.44	4.16	4.2
Sodium	7.3	13.65	14.0

From the analysis it is inferred that the compound contains two sodium atoms in the molecule⁵.

Properties

The compound is white in colour, soluble in water, sparingly soluble in rectified spirit, insoluble in usual organic solvents. The compound does not possess any sharp melting point; it begins to decompose at 230°.

Study of the complexes

The reagent gives water soluble complexes with Fe(III), U(VI), Ti(IV), V(V) and various other metal ions. In case of Fe(III), violet, wine-red and orange-red solutions were produced at different acidities. In case of U(VI), orange-red and orange solutions were produced at different acidities.

Effect of time and stability

The reagent reacts instantaneously with Fe(III) ions to develop the full colour. The violet coloured complex is most unstable and the wine-red complex is most stable but the orange-red complex is intermediate in stability. The reagent has a reducing effect on Fe(III) and hence the colour begins to fade away after sometime.

Experimental

All the reagents used were either of A.R. quality or G.R. quality. Optical densities were measured with a 'Unicam' spectrophotometer using 1 cm quartz cell against water as blank. The pH values of the solutions were measured with an 'Elico' pH meter.

Standard Fe(III) solution

It was prepared from A.R. Ferric ammonium sulphate, standardised and diluted to give a 0.003(M) solution.

Ligand solution

Ligand solutions (0.003 M and 0.009 M) were prepared by direct weighing. The ligand solution in water decomposes on keeping overnight, hence fresh solutions were prepared before use.

Other reagents

The solutions of other reagents were prepared in double distilled water. 5% sulphuric acid (v/v), 5% sodium acetate (w/v), 5% acetic acid (v/v) and 1% sodium hydroxide (w/v) were used for adjusting the pH values.

Spectral characteristics of Fe(III) complexes at different pH values

Spectral curves were drawn at different pH values. Regarding Fe(III) complexes, 3 ml of 0.003 (M) ferric alum solution and 10 ml of 0.003 (M) ligand solution were taken in each of a number of 25 ml. measuring flasks and the pH values were adjusted by adding acetic acid and sodium acetate solutions; volumes were made upto the mark and the pH values were measured by the pH meter. Optical densities of these solutions were measured at different wavelengths from 390 nm to 600 nm (at 10 nm intervals) and against water as blank and plotted against the corresponding wave lengths (Fig. 1). The spectral characteristics of Fe(III) complexes were measured at different pH values from 0.7 to 6.8. Three distinct colours exist within this pH region. At pH values below 2.5, the colour of the complex is purple.

At pH values from 2.7 to 4.1, the colour of the complex is wine-red; at pH values from 4.2 to 6.8, the colour of the complex is orange-red.

Therefore in case of Fe(III) complexes, it has been observed that on increasing the pH of the solution, the absorption peaks are shifted towards lower wavelength i.e., different complexes are formed at different hydrogen ion concentrations.

Fig. 1. Determination of the λ_{max} values.

The curves for the solutions of pH 0.7 to 2.5 represent a violet colour, from 3.5 to 4 wine-red, and from 4.2 to 4.8 orange-red. The sudden shift in the wavelength of the absorbance maxima occurring just above a pH of 2.5 represents the sudden change in colour from violet to wine-red. At an approximate pH of 4.2 the solution becomes orange-red. These abrupt shifts in the position of maximum absorbance strongly indicate that a definite change occurs in the molecular structure of the coloured complexes at the points where the shifts occur⁶. Moreover, this polychromatic property may be applied in analysis to match aliquot parts of a given sample to an orange-red (pH 4.3 to 5.7), wine-red (pH 2.7 to 4.1) or violet (pH 1.2 to 2) standard by the use of suitable buffers to maintain the pH within the range desired.

Composition of the Fe(III) complexes

The compositions of the Fe(III) complexes were determined by Job's method of continuous variation. From the spectral characteristic curves, the λ_{max} at

different pH values were chosen to study the composition.

A number of 25 ml. measuring flasks were taken and equimolecular solutions of Fe(III) and the ligand were prepared separately. The two solutions were mixed as given in the graph plotting. The pH values were adjusted by adding sodium acetate solution, acetic acid, sulphuric acid, sodium hydroxide solutions and the volumes were made upto the mark; then the pH values were measured by the pH meter. The O.D. of the solutions were measured at the selected wavelengths against water as blank. By Job's method, three different complexes of Fe(III) and the ligand have been indicated (as in other cases). In the purple complex, ($\lambda_{max} = 500$ nm, pH = 1.5) Fe : R = 1 : 1; in the wine-red complex ($\lambda_{max} = 480$ nm, pH = 3.5) Fe : R = 1 : 2; whereas in the orange-red complex ($\lambda_{max} = 450$ nm, pH = 4.8) Fe : R = 1 : 3 (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Compositions by Job's method.

complex is comparatively more stable than the other two possibly due to its symmetrical structure (trans position of the two H₂O molecules and trans position of the two ligand units).

Beer's law

Beer's law is obeyed by the most stable wine-red complex (in the pH range 2.7 to 4.1 and at 480 nm) in the concentration range 3 to 23 ppm of Fe (Fig. 3). The molecular extinction coefficient has been found to be 2786 or 2.786×10^3 and the sensitivity of the reaction has been found to be 2.004×10^{-8} . The optimum range, evaluated from the standard curve

was found to be 4 to 13 ppm of Fe. The relative error, as calculated from the Ayres' equation, is 2.73%. Since the violet species is unstable, Beer's law was not studied for it.

Fig. 3. Study of Beer's law.

General procedure

Fe(III) solution containing 100 to 300 ppm of Fe was taken into a 25 cc volumetric flask. A suitable quantity of (5%) acetic acid and (5%) sodium acetate solutions were added so that the pH of the final solution remain in the range of 2.7 to 4.1. 10 cc of 0.5% reagent solution was added and the volume made upto the mark. Absorbances were measured at 480 nm using water as blank.

Effect of diverse ions

To study the interference due to the other ions, solutions were prepared as described for the studies of maximum absorption regions for the complexes, with varying concentrations of foreign ions. Alkali and alkaline earth metal ions e.g., Na⁺, K⁺, Be²⁺, Mg²⁺, Ca²⁺, Sr²⁺, Ba²⁺ do not give any colour reaction and these do not interfere at all. Besides these, the following metal ions also do not interfere—Th⁴⁺, Mn²⁺, Fe²⁺, Zn²⁺, Cd²⁺, Hg²⁺, Al³⁺, Sn²⁺, Pb²⁺, Bi³⁺, Ce⁴⁺. Only in cases of Cr³⁺(20), Co²⁺(20), Ni²⁺(20) and Cu²⁺(20), limiting concentrations have been determined, these being given within the parenthesis (in ppm). Au(III) is however reduced by the reagent. Ti(IV), Zr(IV), V(IV), Mo(VI) do not interfere in the particular pH region mentioned. VO₃⁻, WO₄⁻² and U(VI) interfere seriously. Among the organic ions, acetate does not interfere; but oxalate,

tartrate, citrate, EDTA ion interfere seriously. Besides these F^{-1} , $B_4O_7^{-2}$, PO_4^{-3} also interfere seriously.

References

1. A. K. MAJUMDAR 'N-Benzoyl-phenylhydroxylamine and its Analogues'. International series of monographs in Analytical Chemistry, Vol. 50, Pergamon Press, 1971.
2. N. N. GHOSH and A. CHATTOPADHAY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, 47, 819.
3. S. P. BHARGAVA and N. C. SOGANI, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1971, 36, 255.
4. A. I. VOGEL, A. Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry, 3rd Edition, E.L.B.S. series, p. 589.
5. I. L. FINAR, Organic Chemistry, Vol. I. (E.L. B.S. series) 3rd Edition, 1960, p. 494.